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Analyse the gap between expected service quality and perceived service quality for each identified service quality dimensions

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Abstract

The study's sample included the five biggest private life insurance firms in terms of premium received in FY16. In the private life insurance industry, the top five firms are ICICI Prudential, Bajaj Allianz, HDFC Standard, MAX, and SBI. The data collected from the respondent for each of the five firms was quite similar. A final valid sample size of 431 was achieved from a total of 500 respondents. Statistical packages SPSS (21) and AMOS (21) were used for data analysis. A number of statistical methods were used, including EFA, CFA, SEM, Neural Network Methodology, Independent Samples T-Test, and others. From the total of 431 responses, 355 fell into the "under 30" and "30-40" age brackets, according to the demographic breakdown. Two hundred and fifty-seven men filled out the survey. The vast majority of respondents (212 out of 140) fell into the income bracket of Rs 20,000-50,000, while 140 belonged to the Rs 50,000+ bracket. Most people who took the survey bought policies because their families or friends recommended them to. The vast majority of respondents (276) acquired their policies via agents.

Keywords: Life insurance companies, consumers, service quality, corporation

Introduction

Life insurance companies are starting to catch on to the fact that consumers want better service and may easily switch providers if they aren't satisfied. The fact that disgruntled policyholders easily accept "policy lapses" as an excuse proves this point. Due to a decline in client loyalty, insurance companies must place a premium on managing service quality and customer happiness. In order to maintain or increase their competitive edge, life insurance carriers must rethink their strategy and operations. One important step in this process is to identify ways to build a loyal client base that can withstand intense competition.

Prior to the advent of insurance as a means of reducing taxable income, many Indians put their savings into gold, real estate, and bank accounts. After years of dominance by Life Insurance Corporation, the trend has turned thanks to the Insurance Development Authority Act, 1999 (IRDA), which deregulated the insurance sector and opened the door for private insurance companies with foreign expertise to join the market. These companies now cater to Indian

customers in a more personalised way, making the market more dynamic overall. In addition, a maximum of 26% of Indian insurance companies might be owned by foreign investors. The current level of investment in some private insurance businesses is at 49%.

Literature review

Rai, Priyanka & Mishra, Mr. (2020) ^[1]. Because it safeguards against unforeseen dangers and financial losses, life insurance has become an essential component of contemporary living. From its inception in 1956 until the formation of IRDA in 1999, when the insurance industry was opened to private players, LIC had a stranglehold on the life insurance market. Since customer happiness is crucial for the survival of any firm in today's cutthroat market, and since LIC is now sharing the life insurance field with 23 private competitors, this study intends to analyse the degree of satisfaction of LIC policy holders. According to the results, policyholders are happy with most of the services they get from LIC, but they aren't happy with the

preliminary investigation and medical exam.

Finding and analyzing what makes a difference to life insurance customers in Hanoi is the goal of this research. The study team used SPSS statistical software to evaluate their hypothesis using 259 questionnaire survey samples. Three of the five components of service quality—assurance, tangibles, and responsiveness—have a favourable effect on customer satisfaction, according to the research. However, the association between reliability and empathy, the other two components, is not statistically significant. In order to boost client happiness and encourage the long-term success of insurance companies, the authors have used the study's findings to suggest ways to enhance the standard of insurance services.

Siddiqui (2010) [2] The life insurance industry has just come to terms with the notion that customer service and happiness are the lifeblood of their company. A six-factor instrument for measuring service quality in life insurance is proposed in this study. The dimensions of this instrument include "assurance," "personalised financial planning," "competence," "corporate image," "tangibles," and "technology." The research is based on confirmatory factor analyses. To study how the suggested service quality instrument affects four dimensions of customer happiness—"satisfaction with agents," "satisfaction with functional services," "satisfaction with company," and "overall satisfaction"—a structural equation modelling causal model is recommended. The goal of the suggested framework is to lay out a path forward for life insurance service providers to follow in order to build a loyal client base that is happy with the services they get.

Given the importance of the insurance business to national economies; this study seeks to identify the most important aspects of service quality that influence life insurance customers' happiness. The information was gathered from 557 individuals in northern India who are covered by life insurance contracts. To rank the elements that users consider most important when choosing a life insurance provider, we used a fuzzy analytical hierarchy process (fuzzy-AHP). In this research, certainty, dependability, empathy, responsiveness, and tangibles were the most important characteristics. The study's findings showed that among the factors affecting consumers' choice of life insurance partners, assurance was the most essential, while tangibles were placed last. One disadvantage of the research is that it only included a subset of the SERVQUAL model while analyzing the data collected from north Indian life insurance clients.

Bajpai (2022) [3] Considering LIC's business objectives and plans, the research determines whether the company's life insurance offerings satisfy or beyond customer expectations. Research was limited to the city of Lucknow. Customer satisfaction with LIC services is the intended focus of this report. In only a few short years, innovations in the insurance industry have altered the competitive landscape significantly. Insurance companies now place a premium on satisfying their clients. Customer happiness is quickly rising

to the status of key differentiator and strategic component in an increasing number of sectors. The survey is used to extract important data from the questionnaire. Research papers from journals and magazines are examples of secondary sources. This study provides descriptive information. Improve their feedback system to know client satisfaction level; employ aggressive marketing methods; emphasise more on rural regions; and create new products according to consumer need and desire if LIC wants to boost the life insurance penetration. Everyone from insurance firms to students to professors and academics may benefit from this study. This article presents the model of customer satisfaction with LIC services in a clear and thorough manner at the ground level, where the actual answers from customers were analysed.

Materials and Methods

The bulk of the study activity involves sampling since it is impractical to examine the whole cosmos. This study was also similar in every way. A portion of the population is examined in order to draw conclusions about the whole population. This study's population consisted of private life insurance firms that were members of the IRDA. The research focused on the five largest private life insurance providers in the country. The five leading private life insurance firms in India were as follows: ICICI Prudential, HDFC Standard, Bajaj Allianz, MAX, and SBI. After contacting 500 potential participants, the researcher was able to choose 431 who would be most valuable for the study. All five of the private life insurance firms had 100 people fill out their surveys.

researchers compared private life insurance customers' expectations and perceptions of the discovered service quality characteristics using an independent samples t-test. Once again, we compared client expectations and perceptions across all five private life insurance companies using the independent samples t-test.

Data analysis

Unpaired sample t-test and independent samples t-test are interchangeable terms. Whether comparing two groups, two interventions, or two change scores, the independent samples t test may be used to assess and compare the statistical difference between the means of the two sets of data. Therefore, it is also possible to state that the two separate groups' means are compared to discover statistical evidence of a substantial difference related population mean. For each of the seven factors that fall within the scope of private life insurance companies, we measured the respondents' perceptions and expectations using an independent samples t-test. It was hypothesized—or assumed—for the sake of independent sample statistics that the seven determinants' actual and predicted values would vary.

Consumer expectations and impressions across all seven dimensions were quantified using independent sample statistics, which included measures such as mean, N, standard deviation, and standard error of the mean.

Table 1: Independent Samples Statistics (Private Life Insurance Companies)

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Perceived Tangibility	431	3.29	0.860	0.041
	Expected Tangibility	431	4.54	0.462	0.022
Pair 2	Perceived Reliability	431	3.36	0.838	0.040
	Expected Reliability	431	4.72	0.346	0.017
Pair 3	Perceived Responsiveness	431	3.25	0.855	0.041
	Expected Responsiveness	431	4.64	0.377	0.018
Pair 4	Perceived Assurance	431	3.33	0.865	0.042
	Expected Assurance	431	4.77	0.337	0.016
Pair 5	Perceived Empathy	431	3.09	0.849	0.041
	Expected Empathy	431	4.63	0.392	0.019
Pair 6	Perceived Service Availability	431	3.27	0.983	0.047
	Expected Service Availability	431	4.71	0.362	0.017
Pair 7	Perceived Service Convenience	431	3.17	0.963	0.046
	Expected Service Convenience	431	4.86	0.352	0.017

Perceived tangibility had a mean value of 3.29 and a standard deviation of 0.860, as shown in Table 1. This indicated that customers were rather happy with their impressions. A high mean value of anticipated tangibility of 4.54 was shown. The predicted tangibility has a standard deviation of 0.462. The negative gap for this dimension was caused by the fact that the mean value for anticipation was greater than perception for tangibility. This data suggests that customers were unhappy with the concrete quality of the service they received.

According to Table 1, anticipated dependability had a higher mean value of 4.72 and a standard deviation of 0.346, but perceived reliability had a mean value of 3.36 and a standard deviation of 0.838. A negative gap for the reliability dimension was indicated. Thus, the study's author elucidated the idea that, in terms of the dependability component of service quality, customers had higher expectations and were only moderately happy with the services they actually got. However, when the difference between the expected and actual mean scores was taken into account, it was determined that customers were generally unhappy with the dependability element.

Similarly, customer expectations were 4.64 in the responsiveness scenario, far higher than consumer perceptions (3.25). Perceived responsiveness had a standard deviation of 0.855 and predicted responsiveness of 0.377. Customers' expectations were greater than their impressions when it came to responsiveness, too.

The results revealed that anticipated assurance had a higher mean (4.77 vs. 3.33 for perceived assurance) and a lower standard deviation (0.337 vs. 0.865 for perceived assurance) (Table 1). There was a negative gap for assurance when comparing the mean values of expectation and perception, indicating that consumers were generally unhappy with this component of service quality.

Perceived empathy had a mean value of 3.09 and a standard deviation of 0.849, indicating that customers felt indifferent about the service. As for anticipated empathy, its mean

value was 4.63 and its standard deviation was 0.392. Customer dissatisfaction with the empathy component of service quality was confirmed by higher mean expectation scores compared to mean perception scores.

In comparison to anticipated service availability (4.71), the mean value of perceived service availability (3.27), was lower. Perceived service availability had a larger standard deviation of 0.983 compared to predicted service availability's 0.362. From a perceptual standpoint, buyers were also somewhat happy in this scenario. However, there was a negative difference between the expected and perceived mean scores, thus it's safe to say that consumers were generally unhappy with the service availability component.

It was clear that customers were only somewhat satisfied with the service's perceived ease of use, as the mean value was 3.17 and the standard deviation was 0.963. A high mean score of 4.86 indicates that consumers had high expectations about the ease of the service. Expected service convenience had a standard deviation of 0.352. Customer dissatisfaction with service convenience was a result of greater expectations than perceptions.

The preceding discussion demonstrated that, across all seven categories, private life insurance businesses' actual and anticipated levels of service quality were significantly different. In comparison to customer perceptions, consumer aspirations were much higher across all aspects.

You may see the results of Levene's test for equality of variances and the t-test for equality of two means in an independent sample t-test. The likelihood of a coincidental difference between the two means being 5% or below was determined by a significance value (p-value) of 0.05 or lower. There was a statistically significant difference between the two means. To validate the results of the independent sample statistics and see whether the presumptions needed to be accepted or rejected, an independent sample t-test was used.

Table 2: Independent Samples Test (Private Life Insurance Companies)

S. No.	Service Quality	Hypothesis for	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		Sig.	Mean	Result
	Dimensions	Variances	F	Sig.	T	Df	(2-tailed) Difference		
H ₁	Perceived Tangibility	Equal Variances Assumed	124.728	0.000	-26.545	860	0.000	-1.25	Accepted
	- Expected Tangibility	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-26.545	659.117	0.000	-1.25	
H ₂	Perceived Reliability	Equal Variances Assumed	238.945	0.000	-31.143	859	0.000	-1.09	Accepted
	- Expected Reliability	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-31.143	571.112	0.000	-1.09	
H ₃	Perceived Responsiveness	Equal Variances Assumed	205.969	0.000	-30.790	860	0.000	-1.39	Accepted
	- Expected Responsiveness	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-30.790	591.465	0.000	-1.44	
H ₄	Perceived Assurance	Equal Variances Assumed	243.604	0.000	-32.229	860	0.000	-1.44	
	- Expected Assurance	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-32.229	557.726	0.000	-1.44	
H ₅	Perceived Empathy	Equal Variances Assumed	189.390	0.000	-34.201	860	0.000	-1.54	Accepted
	- Expected Empathy	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-34.201	605.247	0.000	-1.54	
H ₆	Perceived Service Availability	Equal Variances Assumed	285.989	0.000	-28.412	860	0.000	-1.44	Accepted
	- Expected Service Availability	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-28.412	544.797	0.000	-1.44	
H ₇	Perceived Service Convenience	Equal Variances Assumed	346.143	0.000	-34.089	860	0.000	-1.69	Accepted
	- Expected Service Convenience	Equal Variances Not Assumed			-34.089	543.009	0.000	-1.69	

To determine if there were any discrepancies between private life insurance customers' expectations and their actual experiences across all seven aspects of service quality, an independent samples t test was used (see Table 2). Assuming the null hypothesis that the variances of the two groups are not different, Levene's test is performed. In Levene's test, the null hypothesis states that the two groups do not vary significantly in variance. The null hypothesis that the variances of the seven dimensions of service quality were equal was rejected since Levene's test showed that each dimension had a significance value less than 0.05. Therefore, the researcher had utilised the second row, where the variances were not supposed to be equal, to assess the significant difference between the means of the anticipated and perceived aspects of service quality.

According to Table 2, we may accept hypothesis H₁ since the perceived and predicted tangibility had a t-value of -26.545 and a p-value less than 0.05 at the 95% confidence range. So, it's safe to say that consumers' expectations and perceptions of the tangibility component of service quality differed significantly.

When it came to dependability, a t-value of -31.143 and a p-value lower than 0.05 showed that there was a significant difference between the two. As a result, we may accept hypothesis H₂ and state that there was a statistically significant difference between customers' expectations and their judgements of the dependability component of service quality.

All of the following hypotheses were found to be statistically significant: H₃ (Perceived Responsiveness -

Expected Responsiveness), H₄ (Perceived Assurance - Expected Assurance), H₅ (Perceived Empathy - Expected Empathy), H₆ (Perceived Service Availability - Expected Service Availability), and H₇ (Perceived Service Convenience - Expected Service Convenience). The p-values were all less than 0.05. Customers' expectations and impressions of seven aspects of private life insurance firms' service quality differed significantly, confirming all of the previously postulated predictions. Thus, according to table 2, there was a statistically significant difference between the following metrics: expected reliability, perceived tangibility, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, service availability, and service convenience.

There is little variation in the seven aspects of service quality across private life insurance businesses, as shown in table 2. Still, when looking at the mean difference value of the anticipated and perceived dimensions of service quality, the one for service convenience had the highest negative score (1.69). As a result, private life insurance firms had the lowest service quality ratings in terms of client satisfaction with regard to the ease of their policies. The following factors were found to have the largest disparity: service convenience (-1.54), assurance (-1.44), responsiveness (-1.39), tangibility (-1.25), and empathy (-1.54). When it came to the dependability component of their service, private life insurance firms scored a pitiful -1.09. Therefore, as compared to other aspects of service quality, private life insurance businesses were doing better in terms of dependability.

Conclusion

The research included the six main U.P.: Agra, Aligarh, Ambedkar Nagar, Ayodhya, and Amethi. Data was gathered from 500 participants using a questionnaire that included three parts: one assessing the demographic profile, the second the service quality of private insurance businesses, and the third measuring consumer loyalty. All six regions of the National Capital Region were adequately represented in the distribution of surveys. The study's sample included the five biggest private life insurance firms in terms of premium received in FY16. In the private life insurance industry, the top five firms are ICICI Prudential, Bajaj Allianz, HDFC Standard, MAX, and SBI. The data collected from the respondent for each of the five firms was quite similar. A final valid sample size of 431 was achieved from a total of 500 respondents.

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